

Bayes Estimators of Exponentiated Inverse Rayleigh Distribution using Lindleys Approximation

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Abstract

This work presents the results of a joint frequentist and bayesian approach to build Bayes estimators for the missing shape and scale parameters of the Exponentiated Inverse Rayleigh Distribution (EIRD). The shape and scale parameters of an EIRD were determined by applying the Bayes theorem to the posterior distribution. This distribution was tested under various loss functions, including entropy, linex, and scale

invariant squared error, and was found to work with both conjugate and non-conjugate prior distributions. The shape and scale parameters' posterior distributions are difficult, so we used a Lindley approximation to get the ones we care about. Estimates for the size and shape parameters were obtained using the loss function, assuming that the scale and

shape parameters are unknown and independent. Also the Bayes estimate for the simulated datasets and real life datasets were obtained. The Bayes estimates obtained under different loss functions are close to the true parameter value of the shape and scale parameters. The estimators are then compared in terms of their Mean Square Error (MSE) using R programming language. We deduce that the MSE reduces as the sample size (n) increases.

Keywords: Lindley's approximation; posterior distribution; prior distribution; entropy loss

function; linex loss function; scale invariant squared error loss function.

1 Introduction

Rayleigh distribution originated from a two parameters Weibull distribution and it's a suitable model for mdistribution (IRD) was introduced by [1] for modeling realibility and survival data sets. [2] studied some properties of IRD and [3] discussed the properties and maximum likelihood estimation of the scale parameter of IRD. The variance and the higher order moments of this distribution do not exist. The reliability sampling plans of IRD was carried out by [4]. The probability density function (PDF) of the one parameter IRD The closed-form

expressions for the mean, harmonic mean, geometric mean, mode and the median of IRD was discussed by [5]. The estimation of the parameter σ using both different classical and Bayesian estimation methods was carried out by [5] and [6]. In recent years, attention has been shifted to the generalization of probability distribution theory, most applied in reliability estimation [7, 8, 9, 10]. The transmuted Rayleigh distribution and transmuted generalized Rayleigh distribution were developed by [11, 12] respectively. [13] and [14] proposed a Beta Inverse Rayleigh. The exponentiated inverse

Rayleigh distribution (EIRD) also known as a life time distribution was introduced by [15]. This

distribution can be adopted for reliability estimation

and statistical quality control. The probability density function (pdf) of EIRD is written as

Fig. 1. PDF of an EIRD

Fig. 2. CDF of an EIRD

Fig. 3. Reliability graph of an EIRD

Fig. 4. Hazard graph of an EIRD

the Entropy Loss Function, Linex Loss Function and Scale Invariant Squared Error Loss Function given that the scale and shape parameters are unknown. In Sections 2, we discuss the estimation of the shape and scale parameters. In Section 3, numerical results are presented

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Maximum likelihood function

Let $x = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$ be a random variable drawn from EIRD with size n . The likelihood function for the given random sample can be expressed as

for both the simulated and real-life data on survival times of patients with breast cancer, and Section 4 contains the conclusion.

$$L(x/\sigma, \alpha) = 2^n \sigma^n \alpha^n \prod_{i=1}^n x^{-3} e^{-\sum_{i=1}^n (\frac{\sigma}{x})^2} \prod_{i=1}^n (1 - e^{-(\frac{\sigma}{x})^2})^{\alpha-1} \quad (2.1)$$

Table 1. Estimates of the parameters of the four methods MLE, LLF, ELF and SISLF with their MLEs

n	Parameter		MLE		LLF		ELF		SISLF		
	σ	α	σ	α	σ	α	σ	α	σ	α	
20	a=1.3 b=1 k=2	0.5	0.3277 (0.0708)	0.3037 (0.0759)	0.5298 (0.0155)	0.5417 (0.0269)	0.5280 (0.0114)	0.5320 (0.0272)	0.5212 (0.0105)	0.5195 (0.0273)	
		1.2	0.5720 (0.0754)	1.5060 (0.4735)	0.5232 (0.0061)	1.2292 (0.2287)	0.5204 (0.0060)	1.3145 (0.2605)	0.5148 (0.0058)	1.3401 (0.3204)	
		2	0.37725 (0.0561)	1.0128 (0.3028)	0.5190 (0.0047)	2.1340 (0.8753)	0.516 (0.0047)	2.2064 (0.9440)	0.5119 (0.0045)	2.3326 (1.3331)	
	1 a=0.5 b=1.5 k=0.5	2.5	0.8240 (0.1107)	1.6145 (0.5340)	1.0464 (0.0183)	2.8056 (1.6256)	1.0396 (0.0178)	2.7898 (1.7014)	1.0306 (0.0171)	3.0045 (2.5415)	
		1	1.1475 (0.1800)	0.8599 (0.2520)	1.0582 (0.0310)	1.1127 (0.1654)	1.0495 (0.0272)	1.0791 (0.1579)	1.0371 (0.0257)	1.0870 (0.1874)	
		1.5	1.1328 (0.1398)	2.1407 (0.7288)	1.0505 (0.0226)	1.6725 (0.4472)	1.0424 (0.0219)	1.6376 (0.4476)	1.0327 (0.0209)	1.6994 (0.5825)	
	50	a=1.3 b=1 k=2	0.5	0.4793 (0.0565)	0.4612 (0.0766)	0.5024 (0.0015)	0.5033 (0.0018)	0.5022 (0.0009)	0.5021 (0.0018)	0.5015 (0.0008)	0.50033 (0.0018)
			1.2	0.4947 (0.0452)	1.1250 (0.2167)	0.5086 (0.0021)	1.2271 (0.0060)	0.5075 (0.0021)	1.2341 (0.0638)	0.5051 (0.0021)	1.2374 (0.0677)
			2	0.4996 (0.0408)	1.9006 (0.4087)	0.5073 (0.0016)	2.0271 (0.2017)	0.5063 (0.0017)	2.0660 (0.2256)	0.5044 (0.0016)	2.1009 (0.2544)
		1 a=2.5 b=1 k=0.5	2.5	1.1066 (0.0817)	2.9527 (0.6750)	1.0179 (0.0064)	2.6076 (0.4002)	1.0151 (0.0063)	2.5940 (0.4056)	1.0115 (0.0062)	2.6571 (0.4714)
1			1.1063 (0.0976)	1.2834 (0.2524)	1.0226 (0.0102)	1.0421 (0.044)	1.0190 (0.0096)	1.0276 (0.0427)	1.01401 (0.0094)	1.0251 (0.0444)	
1 a=2.5 b=1 k=0.5		1.5	1.0139 (0.0788)	1.8878 (0.3849)	1.0204 (0.0077)	1.5667 (0.1115)	1.0171 (0.0076)	1.5494 (0.1093)	1.0127 (0.0074)	1.5626 (0.1189)	

Table 2. Estimates of the parameters of the four methods MLE, LLF, ELF and SISLF with their MLEs

n	Parameter		MLE		LLF		ELF		SISLF		
	σ	α	σ	α	σ	α	σ	α	σ	α	
100	a=1.3 b=1 k=2	0.5	0.5862 (0.0453)	0.5640 (0.067)	0.5052 (0.0030)	0.5072 (0.0036)	0.5049 (0.0018)	0.5048 (0.0037)	0.5035 (0.0018)	0.5014 (0.0037)	
		1.2	0.4559 (0.0281)	1.2014 (0.1609)	0.5041 (0.0010)	1.2129 (0.0281)	0.5035 (0.0010)	1.2159 (0.0291)	0.5023 (0.0010)	1.2166 (0.0298)	
		2	0.4586 (0.0253)	1.9313 (0.2830)	0.5034 (0.0008)	2.0102 (0.094)	0.5029 (0.0008)	2.0303 (0.1003)	0.5020 (0.0008)	2.0457 (0.1061)	
	1 a=2.5 b=1 k=0.5	2.5	1.0481 (0.0553)	2.3789 (0.3622)	1.0081 (0.0030)	2.5512 (0.1775)	1.0067 (0.0030)	2.5431 (0.1781)	1.0048 (0.0029)	2.5716 (0.1917)	
		1	1.1096 (0.0714)	1.0723 (0.1424)	1.0108 (0.0045)	1.0205 (0.0197)	1.0090 (0.0044)	1.1096 (0.0192)	1.0065 (0.0044)	1.0117 (0.0196)	
		1.5	0.9254 (0.0566)	1.2725 (0.1728)	1.0112 (0.0038)	1.5332 (0.0498)	1.0095 (0.0037)	1.5242 (0.0491)	1.0073 (0.0036)	1.5295 (0.0511)	
	200	a=1.3 b=1 k=2	0.5	0.4926 (0.0285)	0.4769 (0.0393)	0.5024 (0.0017)	0.5038 (0.0018)	0.5024 (0.0009)	0.5023 (0.0018)	0.5017 (0.0008)	0.5001 (0.0018)
			1.2	0.5350 (0.0230)	1.3687 (0.1349)	0.5018 (0.0005)	1.2051 (0.0135)	0.5015 (0.0005)	1.2065 (0.0137)	0.5009 (0.0005)	1.2066 (0.0139)
			2	0.5323 (0.0205)	2.3485 (0.2590)	0.5015 (0.0004)	2.0024 (0.0456)	0.5013 (0.0003)	2.0124 (0.0471)	0.5001 (0.0004)	2.0196 (0.0484)
		1 a=2.5 b=1 k=0.5	2.5	1.0183 (0.0374)	2.7745 (0.3128)	1.0041 (0.0015)	2.5210 (0.0818)	1.0034 (0.0015)	2.5172 (0.0819)	1.0025 (0.0015)	2.5296 (0.0845)
1			1.053 (0.0474)	1.0707 (0.0995)	1.0054 (0.0022)	1.0093 (0.0092)	1.0044 (0.0021)	1.0056 (0.0091)	1.0032 (0.0022)	1.0047 (0.0091)	
1 a=2.5 b=1 k=0.5		1.5	1.0161 (0.0416)	1.6512 (0.1681)	1.0050 (0.0018)	1.5162 (0.0242)	1.0042 (0.0018)	1.5117 (0.0240)	1.0031 (0.0018)	1.5140 (0.0244)	

2.2 Application to Coating weight by chemical method on Tcs and

Bcs.

In this section, the EIRD is applied to two (2) real data sets which were gotten from [15]. The first data set was a 72 observations on coating weight by chemical method on top center side (TCS) and the second data set was 72 observations on coating weight by chemical method on bottom center side (BCS).

For the Tcs data

36.8 47.2 35.6 36.7 55.8 58.7 42.3 37.8 55.4 45.2 31.8 48.3 45.3 48.5 52.8 45.4 49.8 48.2 54.5 50.1
48.4 44.2 41.2 47.2 39.1 40.7 40.3 41.2 30.4 42.8 38.9 34.0 33.2 56.8 52.6 40.5 40.6 45.8 58.9 28.7
37.3 36.8 40.2 58.2 59.2 42.8 46.3 61.2 58.4 38.5 34.2 41.3 42.6 43.1 42.3 54.2 44.9 42.8 47.1 38.9
42.8 29.4 32.7 40.1 33.2 31.6 36.2 33.6 32.9 34.5 33.7 39.9

For the Bcs

45.5 37.5 44.3 43.6 47.1 52.9 53.6 42.9 40.6 34.1 42.6 38.9 35.2 40.8 41.8 49.3 38.2 48.2 44.0 30.4
62.3 39.5 39.6 32.8 48.1 56.0 47.9 39.6 44.0 30.9 36.6 40.2 50.3 34.3 54.6 52.7 44.2 38.9 31.5 39.6
43.9 41.8 42.8 33.8 40.2 41.8 39.6 24.8 28.9 54.1 44.1 52.7 51.5 54.2 53.1 43.9 40.8 55.9 57.2 58.9
40.8 44.7 52.4 43.8 44.2 40.7 44.0 46.3 41.9 43.6 44.9 53.6

The data is summarized in Table 3.

Table 3. Estimates of the parameters of the four methods MLE, LLF, ELF and SISLF with their MLEs for the real life datasets

$$a=3, b=4 \text{ and } k=2$$

Data	MLE		LLF		ELF		SISLF	
	σ	α	σ	α	σ	α	σ	α
Tcs	73.0125	13.1818	71.3211	12.2881	63.1867	12.9297	71.3211	12.9014
Bcs	78.5689	12.2331	76.9089	17.0602	69.1793	17.8291	70.1575	17.8466

Conclusion

In this work, we consider the classical method and Bayesian method under different loss functions such as Entropy Loss Function, Linex Loss Function and Scale Invariant Squared Error Loss Function. We employed the Bayesian techniques to obtain the posterior estimates of an EIRD using both conjugate and non-conjugate prior distribution under different loss functions and adopted the maximum likelihood approach to estimate the two parameter of interest. Fig. 1. shows that the PDF of the EIRD distribution at varying parameter values which shows that the distribution is positively skewed and the Fig. 2. is the CDF which shows the increasing pattern as other distributions. Fig. 3. shows the reliability graph which proves that the distribution can be used in lifetime studies since the graph tends to decrease as the time increases. Fig. 4. shows the hazard graph which shows the upside down bath-tub curve shape.

Table 1 and 2 shows the posterior estimates with MSE under different loss functions for the simulated datasets. Table 3, shows the posterior estimate on the real life dataset (coating weight by chemical method on top center side (TCS) and bottom center side (BCS))for different prior distribution under different loss functions

Based on the results displayed in Tables 1 and 2, we observed that all the posterior estimates for both shape and scale parameters for the simulated datasets are close to the true values of parameters of an EIRD. Also, we discovered the methods are consistent since the values of MSE decrease as

sample size increases. It can be observed that the Bayesian estimates for both scale and shape parameters under the Bayesian techniques perform better than that of the classical techniques. The results obtained under the loss function ELF were quite more efficient than others loss functions because of its smallest MSE.

Acknowledgment

A brief acknowledgement section may be given after the conclusion section just before the references. The acknowledgments of people who provided assistance in manuscript preparation, funding for research, etc. should be listed in this section.

Competing Interests

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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